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Ship model-based route optimisation for decision support in deep sea shipping

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Abstract. We present a new approach and route optimization methodology to support analysis and planning of vessel and fleet performance in deep sea shipping for green, energy efficient, and safe navigation. The developed methodology combines the ship technical characteristics based on a ship model developed for a particular vessel type and energy-saving technology options and an optimization algorithm taking into account weather conditions. Optimization involves two stages: graph construction and Dynamic Programming labelling algorithm implemented to solve the shortest path problem with variable speed. The new approach is implemented as part of a decision-support tool EcoRouter enabling the user to conduct analysis of safe and Pareto optimal solutions. Several applications to support real fleet planning and ship performance analysis have been identified including project engineering for future energy-saving ship technologies, for example, wind-assisted propulsion.

1 Introduction

The tremendous development over the past decade in maritime emissions regulations with constantly stricter requirements at global and regional levels (EEXI, CII, FuelEU, EU-ETS), and an ultimate goal from IMO to reach net zero GHG emissions by 2050 [IMO, 2023], has pushed the maritime industry to take actions and search solutions for real GHG emissions reductions from their ships. Given the constantly increasing maritime freight activity, it has become clear that both carbon-efficiency and energy efficiency together are needed [DNV, 2023]. Although much attention and hope has been attributed these recent years to renewable and low-carbon fuels value, not only is the carbon-free fuel pathway alone not sufficient for the global fleet to reach net zero, but it makes energy efficiency a fundamental factor in its achievement. Given the estimated significant impact of green fuel production of both end fuel costs and primary energy demand [Lindstad et al., 2021], there is a clear need for intensive efforts to reduce the overall consumption. In this quest for greener shipping, ship owners and operators are facing challenges in choosing strategies that ensure compliance with minimum impact on profitability. Besides regulatory pressure and an increasing fuel cost burden (new and more expensive zero-emission energy carriers, reducing profit margins and cost competitiveness), the growing effort on efficiency in fleet operations is also motivated by more stringent requirements from customers pushing for greener supply chains, and a global transport industry easily pointing out inefficient shipping operations responsible for congestion and increased emissions at ports. Energy efficiency measures available for ship owners and operators are basically divided into: technical improvements and operational improvements, traditionally explored and assessed individually as part of cost benefit studies. Notwithstanding, the energy efficiency potential from technical solutions depends on among others on the way it is used during navigation. Present study uses the decision-support tool EcoRouter to demonstrate possibilities for analysis of the effects of new technical solutions on vessel performance using ship-based voyage optimization. Motivation behind the

Ecorouter tool is to provide a transparent method for assessment of green ship technologies under the goal of improving fleet utilization and voyage planning by differentiating ships according to their operational performance potential.

In addition to fleet performance efficiency considerations, looking into the future steps towards a greener and more competitive fleets, ship owners and operators are faced with decisions including many uncertain factors and no well-documented decision basis when making assessments regarding performance of particular ship designs or technologies in real operating and weather conditions. Emerging technologies, as well as larger variations in ship performance within a fleet resulting from the introduction of newbuilds and retrofits are assumed to impact routing decisions and create the need for more assessment methods. The link between technology choice and ship operation therefore needs to become stronger.

Improving knowledge about the economic and environmental impact of new technologies on operations – such as selecting the best ship for a given operations or trade area, or finding the best route for a specific ship considering environmental factors – will strengthen the ship owner's ability to make informed decisions on fleet and ship levels.

Decision support is available only in the form of voyage planning commercial software that usually has as its core A to B ship routing suggestions including the effects of environmental factors, so-called weather routing, with the goals of bad weather avoidance and safety compliance. Commercial products rarely optimise the routes taking weather effects into account as this requires combined expertise from different research fields [Psaraftis et al., 2017]. Voyage optimisation in the pre-voyage stage is currently mainly supported by commercial weather routing software producing route suggestions based on forecast data, and is handled in real time by the bridge team.

This paper presents the results of the research efforts by SINTEF Ocean within the innovation research project EcoRouter conducted in cooperation with experts representing several ship owners and operators involved in various segments of deep sea shipping. The main result has come in the form of a prototype decision support tool for strategic and tactical level fleet decisions based on vessel performance analyses. These are made possible by studying routes produced by the tool's ship model-based route optimisation module. Possible and actual applications of EcoRouter tool are demonstrated on a few routes and vessel particulars. One of the main motivations for tool development was to provide insight into the potential of retrofit options and operational consequences of novel propulsive technologies in terms of optimal routes and speed profiles. EcoRouter's goal is to aid strategic and tactical fleet decisions, particularly for assessment of effects of new ship technologies for higher energy efficiency or fleet deployment, and to support more general vessel performance analysis (post-voyage evaluation, routing strategies etc.).

2 Literature review

Optimizing a ship's voyage is one of the main objectives in shipping company's operations to stay competitive. It is driven by the need to operate a ship as cost efficient, energy efficient and safe as possible during every voyage in its lifetime. Depending on the requirements of the ship's operator the main objective can be to optimize a ship's voyage concerning energy efficiency [Bentin et al., 2016],[Park and Kim, 2015], voyage duration [Kepaptsoglou et al., 2015], safety [Perera and Soares, 2017], or combinations of these aspects [Hinnenthal and Clauss, 2010]. The main optimization methods used in weather routing are the modified isochrone method, dynamic programming, Dijkstra's algorithm, and the application of more complex heuristics [Hinnenthal, 2008]. In [Khan et al., 2022] the authors provide a comprehensive survey on the most recent advances in voyage optimization and claim that co-evolutionary approaches show better performance compared to other methods. The choice of solution algorithm has a crucial effect on the solution quality and computation time. The bulk of academic work on optimization in weather routing concerns specific routes and vessels with weather data for a limited time period. Few commercial products offer route optimization incorporating weather as it requires expertise from both naval architects, meteorologists, optimization algorithm and software developers [Psaraftis et al., 2017]. Also, most commercial systems operate as black boxes giving the user no transparency on the used methods or any choice [Zis et al., 2020], [Rialland and Dæhlen, 2020]. In their study of publications on emission control-driven voyage optimization [Yu et al., 2021] identified the following research gaps: (a) further work needed to identify appropriate mathematical programming methodologies to solve practical voyage optimization (b) Besides further work to handle the challenge of weather forecast uncertainty, there is a need to better consider the constantly varying navigation conditions related to the voyage time. (c) Need to go beyond the shortest path approach, towards more careful route planning and optimization. (d) Need for a more comprehensive and efficient approach to dynamic and efficient voyage optimization. (e) Need to provide more insight to industry about the impact of weather, ship type, displacement and sea state on fuel consumption variation.

The research efforts in the EcoRouter project have combined the necessary expertise from the domains of hydrodynamics and optimization, and with the connection to environmental data aims to aid decision making for ship owners and operators in various applications, while being fully transparent on how route optimisation integrates weather data and its effects on ship performance based on ship model for a particular ship and technology under consideration. Furthermore, in close dialog with ship owners and operators, new applications in decision making of ship model-based route optimisation including weather effects have been identified. These are demonstrated through user case analysis in Chapter 4.

3 Ship model-based routing solution approach

In this section, we provide a description of the ship-model based route optimization solution approach implemented in the decision-support tool *EcoRouter*. The ship model-based routing problem including weather effects considered in this study falls within the broader field of voyage optimization where the common objectives are the optimized travel time and energy/cost/fuel consumption. We handle the safety implicitly via respective constraints. In optimization terms the problem can be classified as the bi-objective resource-constrained shortest path problem with variable speed and weather conditions. The use of two objectives implies that the solution to the problem is represented by a set of Pareto optimal solutions rather than a single one.

3.1 Main inputs

The following data and parameters are used as an input to solution approach:

- A *reference route* which is defined by a list of waypoints where the first waypoint is the origin and the last way point is the destination location (see Figure 1).
- *Departure time options*. The reason of having a list rather than a single departure time is to find a more favorable weather window resulting in a more energy efficient and safe solution.
- *Expected time of arrival* (ETA) window defined as the earliest and latest expected time of arrival, EETA and LETA correspondingly. Although, usually only the latest time of arrival is considered, setting the limit on the maximal voyage duration, we use an ETA window to account for port of arrival limitations.
- *Weather data*. The weather data is included in the form of estimate values for the wind, wave and sea currents. This can be either historical data or forecast.
- *Vessel characteristics*. Taking into account that one of the objectives is the energy consumption minimization, an energy consumption function or a numerical model reflecting the vessel's performance is required.
- *Safety limitations*. Safety thresholds are defined by critical values of weather conditions' estimates when it is either prohibited to sail or some action such as speed change is required.
- Minimum S^{min} and maximum S^{max} allowed *vessel speed*. These parameters discard the search for the unreasonably low and high speeds and avoid energy consumption function to extrapolate the values outside its domain.
- *Geo data*. Coastal line of continents and islands is required to define the search area which in the context of the problem is the open sea. Although, navigational maps are available for maritime transportation we limit our study only to the use of the coastal lines data.

3.2 Optimization

As a solution approach to solve the bi-objective routing problem we apply Dynamic Programming (DP) labeling algorithm which implies breaking the problem into simpler sub-problems and solving the complete problem in a recursive manner.

3.2.1 Graph construction Compared to the vehicle routing problem where the routing decisions are defined by the road network, the weather routing decisions, in theory, can be based on an infinite number of choices. In the proposed methodology, the main idea of how to explore all potential vessel sailing options, is to construct a graph covering a certain corridor around the *reference route* (see Figure 1). The graph construction is based on the generation of sets of waypoints in the direction perpendicular to the vessel's heading along the *reference route*. The crucial decisions involve the graph size and structure which define combinatorial complexity and solution accuracy. The *reference route* is subdivided into relatively equal segments by generating a list V of waypoints (nodes in the graph context) where the first and the last nodes are the origin and the destination. We further use $n = |V|$ to refer the number of waypoints in V .

Figure 1: Graph construction parameters

Let $N = \{N[l] | l \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}\}$ be the compound set of nodes where each set $N[l]$ is associated with a waypoint number l in V (see Figure 1). In the DP context each set $N[l]$ is associated with stage number $l \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$. Let $G(W, A)$ be the directed acyclic graph where W is the set of graph nodes and A is the set of graph arcs. The set N in the context of graph G is defined as $N = \{N[l] | l \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}, N[l] \subset W\} = W$. Sets $N[0]$ and $N[n-1]$ are limited to contain only one waypoint, origin $V[0]$ and destination $V[n-1]$ further referred to as o and e correspondingly. To reduce the number of arcs, they are generated only between adjacent sets $N[l]$ and $N[l+1]$. For each node $i \in W$ we define set of arcs $A(i) = \{(i, j) \subset A, i \in N[l], j \in N[l+1], l \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}\}$.

We further define parameter θ^{max} controlling the maximum distance of the generated way points from the voyage legs and parameter θ^{step} defining the distance between nodes in $N[l], l \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$. Parameter ϵ defines the branching factor i.e. the maximum number of output arcs a graph node can have (the minimum is limited to 1). Nodes which are not located in an open sea and arcs crossing a land mass are discarded from the graph.

3.2.2 DP labeling algorithm The developed graph structure allows to implement stage-wise DP labeling algorithm where starting from the origin node o of stage 0, the algorithm recursively explores potential sailing options for all nodes $i \in N[l] \subset W, l \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$ at the subsequent stage by referencing their respective arcs set $A(i) \subset N[l+1], l \in 0, \dots, n-1$ and storing a partial options data in the respective labels. A label associated with partial path or a sub-problem in DP terms is defined as $L = (i, t, c, l, s, s^{Counter})$ where i is the current node, t is the total sailing time, c is total energy consumed, l is leg or stage number for node i . Set $s = \{s_y | y \in \{0, \dots, l\}\}$ defines the speeds combination of individual legs speed l_y along the path up to the node i . $s^{Counter}$ tracks the number of times the speed has been changed. The decisions variables considered in the algorithm are:

- Sailing direction. The options are defined by the graph arcs.
- The speed selection along a voyage leg (graph arc). The speed between any two nodes is assumed to be constant. Set S of a leg speed options is generated with a step s^{step} between minimum S^{min} and maximum S^{max} vessel speed. The number of speed options is controlled by parameter σ and s^{step} is defined as $s^{step} = (S^{max} - S^{min})/\sigma$. Then S can be defined as $S = \{S^{min}, S^{min} + s^{step}, \dots, S^{max}\}$. The value of σ is defined experimentally during the tool calibration.
- Departure time. Departure options are defined by set D which is given as an input.

3.2.3 Resource extension functions Extending a label L_1 from stage l along arc (i, j) with speed u gives a label L_2 such that:

$$s(L_2) = s(L_1) ++ \{u\} \quad (1)$$

$$t(L_2) = t(L_1) + \frac{\text{distance}(i, j)}{u} \quad (2)$$

$$c(L_2) = c(L_1) + f^c(i, j, u, t(L_1)) \quad (3)$$

$$s^{\text{Counter}}(L_2) = \begin{cases} s^{\text{Counter}}(L_1) + 1 & \text{if } u \neq s_l(L_1) \\ s^{\text{Counter}}(L_1) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$l(L_2) = l(L_1) + 1; \quad (5)$$

where expression 1 defines the speed selection and appends u to $s(L_1)$. Expressions 2 and 3 define time and energy calculation correspondingly, where function $f^c(i, j, u, t)$ gives the energy consumption for an arc (i, j) with speed u and sailing starting at time t (see Section 3.5 for details). Expression 4 ensures the speed change counter s^{counter} update if the arc's speed is different from the previous $s_l(L_1)$. The label for the origin node is then initialized as:

$$L(i = o, t = d, c = 0, l = 0, s = \{ \}, s^{\text{Counter}} = 0), \quad \forall d \in D \quad (6)$$

Departure times in set D are specified relatively the earliest departure time which is 0.

3.2.4 Extension feasibility Extending label L_1 along arc (i, j) with speed u producing label L_2 is feasible if:

$$t(L_2) \leq \text{LETA} - \begin{cases} \frac{\text{distance}(j, e)}{S^{\text{max}}} \\ \text{if } s^{\text{Counter}}(L_2) < s^{\text{countermax}} \\ \frac{\text{distance}(j, e)}{s_l(L_2)} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$s^{\text{counter}} \leq S^{\text{countermax}} \quad (8)$$

$$\Gamma(i, j, u, t(L_1)) \leq \Gamma^{\text{crit}} \quad (9)$$

Condition (7) checks that there potentially exists an extension of label L_2 from node j to destination e that arrives at e no later than the LETA. Parameter $s^{\text{countermax}}$ is introduced to avoid exponential growth of the number of labels and defines the maximum number of times the speed can be changed for a path which is ensured by condition 8. Condition (9) ensures that the weather conditions are within the safety limits for the given arc, speed and time. This is further described in Section 3.5.1.

3.2.5 Dominance definitions Given the bi-objective function, the solution to the problem is represented by a Pareto set of optimal solutions. Classical approach would be to filter out dominated paths ending at the same node and thus to reduce the rapid growth of their number. In this case, the dominance condition $L_1 \prec L_2$ for labels with the same node holds true if:

$$t(L_1) \leq t(L_2) \quad (10)$$

$$c(L_1) \leq c(L_2) \quad (11)$$

However, the weather conditions make it practically impossible to define if any non-dominated partial path is a part of any non-dominated complete path. The opposite is true, a dominated partial path may result, for some sequence, in non-dominated path. Thus, an assumption is made that by filtering out dominated labels according to 10 and 11 we discard less promising labels what makes this approach a more heuristic. Nevertheless, it makes less sense to compare paths ending at the same node and having different speeds combination or departure time. Conditions of sailing to the node are too different and a lot of promising solutions might be discarded. Therefore, to increase the number of paths for the exploration, while keeping the balance between the number of labels growth and solution quality, the dominance check for the labels at the same node is performed if the paths have the same speeds combination. Conditions 10 and 11 are then complemented by:

$$s(L_1) = s(L_2) \quad (12)$$

It is worth noting that condition 12 is ensured only for partial paths. Requirement for the labels to have the same departure time is ensured by the separation of the search for each departure time (see Algorithm 2).

Non-efficient labels i.e. those dominated by others ending at the same node and having the same speeds combination are discarded in a dominance check step.

3.3 DP labeling algorithm for bi-objective shortest path

The pseudo code of the DP labeling algorithm is provided in Algorithms 1 and 2. Algorithm 1 executes initialization of the label for the origin node at departure time d . Algorithm 2 provides the pseudo code of the optimization procedure. After the initialization step the algorithm, in a while cycle iteration, evaluates the options of extending labels in set $R^{current}$ having labels with nodes at stage i to the next stage $i + 1$. Extension of a label to the next stage $i + 1$ takes place by referencing the set of nodes in $A(w)$ (defining outgoing arcs) of its current node w . Each arc option is assessed with speed $u \in S$ based on how many times the speed was changed for the current path. After the calculation of time t and energy c a new potential label L^{new} is obtained. If the label is feasible (conditions 7 8 and 9) then the non-dominance condition is checked. For practical purposes, non-dominated labels for partial paths with the same node $j(L)$ and speed option $s(L)$ are stored in respective Pareto set $P(j, s(L))$. If the new label is non-dominated all dominated labels in $P(j, s(L))$ are discarded from this set. For the destination node the algorithm stores non-dominated solutions in set $P(e)$ irrespective of the speeds combination. The algorithm returns set P of all non-dominated solutions for all departure times.

Algorithm 1 Initialize(d)

- 1: For each $w \in W$ define distance and heading of its outgoing arcs to nodes $A(w)$.
 - 2: Let $R^{init} = \emptyset$ be the set of initial labels at stage 0;
 - 3: Let $L(i = o, t = d, c = 0, l = 0, s = \{\}, s^{Counter} = 0)$ be the initial label at departure time d ;
 - 4: $R^{init} \leftarrow R^{init} \cup L$;
 - 5: **return** R^{init} ;
-

Algorithm 2 DP labeling algorithm

- 1: P Pareto set of solutions for all departure times;
 - 2: **for** $d \in D$ **do**
 - 3: $R^{current} \leftarrow initialize(d)$, (Algorithm 1);
 - 4: **while** $i < n - 2$ **do**
 - 5: **for** $L^{cur}(w, t, c, i, s, s^{counter}) \in R^{current}$ **do**
 - 6: **for** $j \in A(w)$ **do**
 - 7: **for** $u \in S$ **do**
 - 8: $L^{new} \leftarrow L^{cur}$ to j with speed u ;
 - 9: **if** L^{new} is feasible **then**
 - 10: Dominance check of L^{new} for $P(j, s(L^{new}))$;
 - 11: $i + +$;
 - 12: $R^{current} \leftarrow$ labels of stage i ;
 - 13: Dominance check of solutions in $P(e)$ for P ;
 - 14: **return** P ;
-

3.4 Weather data

The weather data is provided for the geographical region defined by the graph extreme coordinates and the time span between the earliest departure and latest arrival time (LETA). In what follows we define set $\Omega(m, w)$ of weather estimates at graph node $w \in W$ at time interval number m . All time intervals have the same duration of δ time units (usually 1 hour). Within the optimization, for any fractional time of t hours after departure, the respective time interval number m is calculated as $m = \lfloor t/\delta \rfloor$ i.e the respective nearest. The weather conditions are assumed to be constant within the interval δ and we recall again that the vessel's speed along an arc is constant. The weather estimates are not limited to a particular set and can be tailored to any specific set based on how the energy or any other cost function is calculated.

3.5 Energy calculation

The vessel's power required to maintain a certain speed is a function $f^p(\Omega(t, i), u, \lambda)$ of the speed u , heading λ , weather estimates $\Omega(m, i)$ at particular time interval number m and location i . The power

calculation function performs interpolation of the power value for the actual inputs based on the input file values. The energy c computation, required to cover a certain distance l with a certain speed s is defined as power f^p multiplied by the sailing time $t = (l/s)$ i.e. $c = f^p \cdot t$. Thus, knowing the speed u and weather change time interval δ , a voyage leg's (i, j) sailing time $t(i, j, u)$ can be subdivided into K number of segments corresponding to the weather change. We assume that $\Omega(m, p)$ at any location p along the arc (i, j) is interpolated between $\Omega(m, i)$ and $\Omega(m, j)$ values. Parameter $t_k, k \in \{0, \dots, K-1\}$ defines the beginning of the time segment number k along the leg. The first and the last time segments may be less than δ hours and calculated based on the arc start and end sailing time. The rest of the time segments are exactly δ hours. Let parameter δ_k be the duration of the time interval number k starting at time t_k . The energy required to sail along the arc's (i, j) segments is then:

$$c_k = f^p(\Omega_k, u, \lambda)\delta_k, \quad k \in \{0, \dots, K-1\} \quad (13)$$

where Ω_k is the set of weather estimates for time segment number k defined by interpolation between $\Omega(m, i)$ and $\Omega(m, j)$. Current time interval number m is defined as $m = \lfloor t_k/\delta \rfloor$. For segment number $k = 0$ the time t_0 equals to the arrival at node i . The energy required to sail along arc (i, j) with speed u starting at time t_0 is then:

$$f^c(i, j, u, t_0) = \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} c_k; \quad (14)$$

It is worth of noting that energy calculation can be substituted with any other objective such as fuel, cost, emissions etc.

3.5.1 Safety considerations To comply with safety rules and regulations a vessel may adjust its course and speed to avoid regions with *heavy* weather conditions i.e. inappropriate for sailing or performing an operation. The restrictions on sailing within a *heavy* weather region are defined by the compound set $Q = \{q[j] | j \in \{0, \dots, J-1\}\}$ of J number of combinations of the values of critical weather estimates. For example, there are two combinations of estimates for significant wave height (H_s) and wind speed (W_s):

- $q[0] = \{H_s : 5, W_s : 15\}$
- $q[1] = \{W_s : 25\}$.

This means that if either both wave height and wind speed exceed critical values of 5 meters and 15 m/s respectively or just the wind speed exceeds 25 m/s the weather conditions are considered to be *heavy*. During the optimization, such check is performed for each leg sailing option estimation.

Taking into account that the leg is subdivided into segments according to the weather change, the heavy weather conditions are defined for each leg segment. Let $\gamma_i, i \in \{0, \dots, K-1\}$ be a binary $[0, 1]$ parameter taking value 1 if there is *heavy* weather conditions on a segment number i , 0 otherwise. Then, parameter

$$\Gamma(i, j, u, t) = \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \gamma_k/K \quad (15)$$

defines the total heavy weather score along a voyage leg. Parameter $\Gamma^{crit} = [0, \dots, 1]$ defines the critical value for Γ as the heavy weather tolerance threshold for a leg. The value of Γ^{crit} is subjective and used as an input parameter to the algorithm. Thus, the heavy weather leg feasibility condition can be defined by the following condition:

$$\Gamma \leq \Gamma^{crit} \quad (16)$$

If the condition is satisfied then it is allowed to sail along the leg. Higher values of Γ^{crit} means that for a larger fraction of a leg's sailing time the heavy weather conditions are allowed. If the value is set to 0 then if the heavy weather conditions are observed on at least one leg's segment the leg is discarded as a sailing option.

3.6 Parameters tuning

DP labeling algorithm was coded in Java using parallelization to speed up the search. The tool is deployed on Azure Cloud under Premium v3 P2V3 service plan with 4 virtual CPUs and 16 GB RAM. Table 1 shows tuned parameters and their respective values which were found to be the most appropriate for the CPU time, solution quality and RAM utilization. There were used 10 training instances to collect

statistics. On, average the graph has 2350 nodes and 11800 arcs and it takes 850 seconds to run the algorithm (including weather files download and graph construction) using 8 GB of RAM.

$ V $	θ^{max}	θ^{step}	ϵ	σ
50	450	8	5	10

Table 1: Tuned parameters values

4 Application cases

The ship model-based route optimization solution described in the previous section is implemented in the EcoRouter decision-support tool enabling the study of optimal routes and vessel performance for given voyage scenarios and specific vessel models.

In the following, the use of the tool is demonstrated by two cases each illustrating a particular application: one of a project engineering approach aimed to explore the potential benefits of ship technical improvements; and one operational approach aimed to study the energy saving potential of voyage optimization, flexible scheduling and speed range, considering the impacts of weather and ship characteristics.

The vessel model used for both user cases is representative of a conventional bulk carrier. The data file containing all data points of the vessel's power estimates required to maintain a certain speed at a certain direction under different weather conditions, and used as input for the route optimization, has been pre-generated based on the reference ship SINTEF Ocean Bulk Carrier SOBC-1 [Krasilnikov and Skjefstad, 2023].

Weather data used in route optimization for both cases was retrieved from the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem providing open and free access Earth observation data.

4.1 User case 1: Impact of new technology

In this user case the tool is used as strategic decision support to study the saving potential of a new technology or a particular vessel characteristic taking into account ocean conditions and the vessel's operational context, by identifying the most optimal routes for or most beneficial use of this particular vessel. The main hypothesis is that the extent to which a ship characteristic or particular energy-saving technology affects the ship's energy consumption under voyage depends on the route choice. The approach used in this case study is a comparison of optimal route choices for two vessel options, one conventional bulk carrier, and the same ship equipped with a wind-assisted propulsion system. This user case serves to demonstrate the use of the route optimization tool in which the numerical ship model is used as input only. No analysis of the ship's characteristics or its performance is intended here, nor of the specific propulsion system considered. To demonstrate the process of analysis of potential savings from an alternative propulsion system, our route optimization method is applied to various voyage scenarios. Focusing on one geographic area, the South Atlantic, both westbound and eastbound directions as well as seasons are considered in order to illustrate the variation in weather conditions.

The input voyage scenarios are:

- *Route*: South Atlantic Eastbound and Westbound: Brazil to/from South Africa.
- *Time periods*: January, April, July, and October 2023. Departure day is the 1st of the month.
- *Hindcast metocean data* is used to ensure full data coverage, and to correspond with the intended use for a broader analysis, not a future route planning or weather routing.
- *Speed range*: 12-14 knots with 0.2 knots step.
- *Vessel models*: Conventional and wind-assisted ships.

In total, 16 route optimization scenarios are run, 8 with the conventional and 8 with the wind-assisted ship model (each both directions and for four distinct departure dates). Running each route optimization scenario produces a set of optimal routes for the specific ship model.

Fig 2 provides a screenshot of the output of the route optimization performed in the EcoRouter tool for one of the eight scenarios for the conventional ship: January 2023, eastbound.

In this scenario, 21 distinct routes have been identified as Pareto-optimal. The fastest one takes 245 hours for a distance of 3433 nm, which is 47 hours and 65nm less than the route with the lowest consumption, at 40% higher energy consumption.

Fig. 3 illustrates the results for Pareto-optimal routes for January scenarios with both ship models.

For each scenario the fastest and the lowest energy consumption route characteristics are presented in Fig. 4 summarizing their main performance indicators: total energy consumption (in MWh), distance traveled, duration in days, postponed ETD (in hours) compared to scenario input, average speed (along the route, in knots). The names on the X axis are use as label for each of the scenarios: W for westbound,

Figure 2: Route optimization results for the eastbound South Atlantic voyage with the conventional ship, January 2023

Figure 3: Pareto-optimal routes of each ship model for the South Atlantic voyage, January 2023.

Number for the month of departure of the route, and C or F for labelling Lowest consumption route and Fastest route respectively. This illustrates the variation in energy consumption between optimal routes for the same voyage direction between the conventional ship model and the wind-assisted one. This case is made for demonstration purposes, the results presented represent only a few observations and cannot be generalized.

4.2 User case 2: Impact of voyage optimization

In this user case, the EcoRouter tool is used as a support for analysis of ship operation aiming to quantify the saving potential from voyage optimization. The purpose is to enable the study of optimal routes depending on various operational strategies such as a wider speed range (allowing the ship to deviate from the speed agreement) or of more flexible scheduling (identifying optimal routes based on flexible departure and arrival time). Such application for exploring distinct voyage optimization strategies is relevant for identifying the savings potential from navigation but also in the negotiation among parties involved in voyage optimization and planning of port arrival.

Route optimization with speed options: The voyage scenario used for this user case is Rotterdam to

Figure 4: Summary of main results from each route optimization scenario with each ship models

New Orleans with the expected departure on April 1st 2023, and speed range for optimization either fixed at any integer value between 10 to 15 knots or flexible between 10 and 15 knots. Similar to the previous user case, the EcoRouter tool is used to generate optimal routes for each speed constraint. Fig. 5 presents the output screenshot of the optimal routes with fixed speeds, the blue and black lines corresponding to the fastest and lowest consumption routes respectively. As explained in Chapter 3, several options for departure time are considered, meaning that the optimal routes may suggest a postponed departure time of 0, 12 or 24 hours.

Figure 5: Screenshot of route optimization results for a North Atlantic voyage scenario with speed range 10-15 knot, January 2023

To further illustrate the analytical possibilities provided by the EcoRouter tool and its capability to study potential savings (fuel / time) from more flexible voyage planning, all the optimal routes generated for this particular scenario are displayed in a scatter diagram depicted in Fig. 6. The large blue dots represent the optimal routes from the 10-15 speed range optimization, postponed departure indicated by darker colors. The connecting line is the Pareto front from all optimal routes. The smaller dots

correspond to the routes that are optimized with fixed speed: 10 kn in green, 11kn in grey, 12 kn in pink, 13 in red, 14 in yellow, also with darker colors indicating postponed departure. The results marked with a quadrant indicate the routes, among the pareto optimal ones, that have the longest sailed distance and the lowest consumption, thus CII favorable.

Figure 6: Pareto optimal route characteristics for the North Atlantic voyage scenario considering both fixed and variable speed constraints

The routes for this voyage scenario optimized with fixed and variable speed options, vary between 4460 and 4568 nm in length, 12 and 19 days in duration, and 2250 and 850 Mwh power consumption.

Among the set of routes optimized based on a 10-15kn speed range (the blue series), the majority have duration below 15 days and average speed above 12kn which requires a postponed departure to give lowest possible consumption and navigation time. Comparing the two quickest routes, the light blue (no postponed ETD) with the next best one in dark blue with an ETD postponed by 24h, illustrates how an energy saving of 8% can potentially be achieved by adapting the voyage schedule.

In addition to the set of optimal routes identified that enables comparison between fastest and lowest consumption solutions, Ecorouter offers the possibility to identify and compare the optimal results with the shortest path with lowest consumption option, and can be used to study the potential benefit of considering weather conditions also in tactical decision making when studying routes and voyage planning strategies.

This becomes even more relevant in the CII regulation context. Considering the power need and distance, the routes can be assessed according to their potential CII rating. Looking at the Pareto-optimal fixed-speed routes, the difference between the fastest route and the most CII advantageous ones indicates a potential saving in consumption of around 10%, for a negligible increase in duration (2%, less than 12 hours). This highlights the value of this route optimization tool enabling searching for routes that both contribute to improving CII rating while not affecting commercial constraints.

The possibility to adjust the speed constraints enables the study of potential from route optimization considering not only real meteocean conditions but also important operational and contractual aspects playing a certain role in shipping operational efficiency. Bearing in mind that the data labels for the routes optimised for a 10-15kn speed range indicate an average speed, we see from Fig. 6 the largest opportunity to identify energy- and time-efficient routes when considering speed variation during voyage.

5 Conclusions

The presented ship model-based route optimization methodology put in a broader context of the decision-support tool EcoRouter enables the study of optimal routes and vessel performance considering specific ship characteristics from a particular ship model and real sea and weather conditions. A set of time- and energy- optimal routes, varying in path, speed during voyage and departure schedule, can be identified for a specific vessel and energy saving technology for given weather conditions. Route optimisation results have been presented for two user cases demonstrating new possible applications for distinct decision

making processes, in contrast to a more traditional weather routing perspective. Further work includes exploring more applications within a broader fleet management context. For example, differentiating energy and emission efficient routes taking into account commercial context and requirements, like ballast vs laden voyage. Looking into a more operational use i.e. passage planning, accounting for weather forecast uncertainty, helping vessels set up a navigation plan as robust as possible against weather uncertainty, varying port schedules, contractual and regulatory constraints.

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References

- [Bentin et al., 2016] Bentin, M., Zastrau, D., Schlaak, M., Freye, D., Elsner, R., and Kotzur, S. (2016). A new routing optimization tool-influence of wind and waves on fuel consumption of ships with and without wind assisted ship propulsion systems. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 14:153–162.
- [DNV, 2023] DNV (2023). *Energy Transition Outlook 2023: A global and regional forecast to 2050*.
- [Hinnenthal, 2008] Hinnenthal, J. (2008). *Robust Pareto-optimum routing of ships utilising deterministic and ensemble weather forecasts*. Phd thesis, Technischen Universitat, Berlin, Germany.
- [Hinnenthal and Clauss, 2010] Hinnenthal, J. and Clauss, G. (2010). Robust pareto-optimum routing of ships utilising deterministic and ensemble weather forecasts. *Ships and Offshore Structures*, 5(2):105–114.
- [IMO, 2023] IMO (2023). *Resolution MEPC.377(80). 2023 IMO strategy on reduction of GHG emissions from ships*.
- [Kepaptsoglou et al., 2015] Kepaptsoglou, K., Fountas, G., and Karlaftis, M. G. (2015). Weather impact on containership routing in closed seas: A chance-constraint optimization approach. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 55:139–155.
- [Khan et al., 2022] Khan, S., Grudniewski, P., Muhammad, Y. S., and Sobey, A. J. (2022). The benefits of co-evolutionary Genetic Algorithms in voyage optimisation. *Ocean Engineering*, 245:110261.
- [Krasilnikov and Skjefstad, 2023] Krasilnikov, V. and Skjefstad, V. (2023). Sobc-1 – an open science validation dataset for conventional and windassisted ship propulsion. In *25th Numerical Towing Tank Symposium (NuTTS)*, Ericeira, Portugal.
- [Lindstad et al., 2021] Lindstad, E., Lagemann, B., Rialland, A., Gamlem, G. M., and Valland, A. (2021). Reduction of maritime ghg emissions and the potential role of e-fuels. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 101:103075.
- [Park and Kim, 2015] Park, J. and Kim, N. (2015). Two-phase approach to optimal weather routing using geometric programming. *Journal of Marine Science and Technology*, 20:679–688.
- [Perera and Soares, 2017] Perera, L. P. and Soares, C. G. (2017). Weather routing and safe ship handling in the future of shipping. *Ocean Engineering*, 130:684–695.
- [Psaraftis et al., 2017] Psaraftis, H., Morales Llamas, J., Ding, L., and Nehammer, J. (2017). Blue-siros project wp3, proof of concept. Technical report, BlueSIROS project technical report, Technical University of Denmark.
- [Rialland and Dæhlen, 2020] Rialland, A. and Dæhlen, J. (2020). Rutesim – simulation-based route planning demo presentation. In *SFI Smart Maritime Webinar on Simulation Platforms*.
- [Yu et al., 2021] Yu, H., Fang, Z., Fu, X., Liu, J., and Chen, J. (2021). Literature review on emission control-based ship voyage optimization. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, 93:102768.
- [Zis et al., 2020] Zis, T. P., Psaraftis, H. N., and Ding, L. (2020). Ship weather routing: A taxonomy and survey. *Ocean Engineering*, 213:107697.